

On the Optimum Design of Composite Ducts and Cylinders under Combined Loading

Jacky Prucz, J. Sivan and P. C. Upadhyay

Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering

West Virginia University

Morgantown, WV 26506-6101

Abstract

The optimum (minimum) wall thickness of a composite cylinder / duct required to withstand a combined loading of internal pressure, bending moment, transverse shear, axial and torsional type has been determined. The analysis is based on 2-D lamination theory and accounts for the coupling effect between the loads. Quadratic stress interaction criteria of failure are applied to find the minimum number of plies (duct thickness) needed to withstand a broad range of loading conditions. The model is based on the approach outlined by Tsai for converting the cylinder cross-section to an equivalent box type cross-section. The best fiber angle for angle-ply lay-ups is studied with respect to the variations in the individual load components and material properties. The effect of buckling is highlighted.

KEYWORDS: Design Methodology, Failure Criterion, Optimization, Laminated Plate Theory, Parametrization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are increasingly used in structural applications due to their performance advantages and rising level of confidence in their utilization under a broad range of service conditions. In spite of tremendous progress in the areas of macro and micro level analytical capability to analyze the behavior of composite materials and structures, there is a lack of design models which may allow efficient tailoring of their configurations to specific requirements for structural components. Analytical solutions (1,2,3,4,5) that are available for the analysis of composite cylinders using Shell theory or Elasticity approach are limited to some specific sets of boundary and loading conditions, and are usually quite involved to be used in a typical design environment. Also, in these solutions, the objective is usually to study the stresses and strains under a given load and for a fixed geometry (thickness and radius) of the cylinder.

This paper presents an approach to characterize the response of a composite duct subjected to arbitrary complex boundary conditions and loadings, in an effort to optimize rapid selection of design parameters that minimize the number of plies required from the strength view-point.

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND METHOD OF APPROACH

A composite duct subjected to a combination of shear force, axial force, bending moment, torsional force and internal pressure may be simplified to an equivalent box type configuration proposed by Tsai(6) for design purposes. Figure (1) represents the equivalent configuration for an elliptical cross section duct.

Figure.1: (a) elliptical cross section (b) Equivalent box cross section

Where ,

$$I_{eq} = \frac{\pi h(3a^2b + a^3)}{32} ; \quad b_{eq} = \frac{\pi(a+3b)}{16} ;$$

'h' is wall thickness of the duct, 'a' is outer radius of the duct, 'I_{eq}' is equivalent moment of Inertia of the transformed cross section, 'b_{eq}' is equivalent width of the cross section, 'a' is major and 'b' is minor diameter of the elliptical cross-section. For circular cross-sections this becomes of the following form.

$$I_{eq} = \frac{\pi h a^3}{8} ; \quad b_{eq} = \frac{\pi a}{4} ;$$

For applied axial compressive force F, internal pressure P, transverse shear force V, torque T and bending moment M, equivalent loading referred to transformed configuration can be given by :

$$N_1 = \frac{PR_O}{2} + \frac{F}{2\pi R_O} ; \quad N_2 = PR_O ; \quad N_6 = \frac{V}{\pi R_O} + \frac{T}{2\pi R_O^2}$$

and

$$M_1 = \frac{2M}{\pi R_O}$$

Where N₁ is axial load, N₂ is load due to hoop stress, N₆ is shear load and M₁ is bending moment.

For better and more general comparison between the relative effects of various parameters, all

loadings, material constants and dimensions in this paper have been non-dimensionalized as per the scheme described below.

All length dimensions are non-dimensionalized with respect to outer radius R_0 and all the stiffness and strength constants are non-dimensionalized with respect to the yield strength, X , of the composite in longitudinal tension. All quantities in this paper with upper bars represent non-dimensionalized values. These are:

$$\bar{N}_1 = \frac{P}{2X} + \frac{F}{\pi XR^2_0}; \quad \bar{N}_2 = \frac{P}{X}; \quad \bar{N}_6 = \frac{V}{\pi XR^2_0} + \frac{T}{2\pi XR^3_0};$$

$$\text{and } \bar{M}_1 = \frac{2M}{\pi XR^3_0}$$

Non-dimensional material parameters α_i and β_i have been defined as:

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{X'}{X}; \quad \alpha_2 = \frac{Y}{X}; \quad \alpha_3 = \frac{Y'}{X}; \quad \alpha_4 = \frac{S}{X};$$

$$\beta_1 = \frac{X}{E_X}; \quad \beta_2 = \frac{E_Y}{E_X}; \quad \beta_3 = \frac{G_{XY}}{E_X};$$

3. SOLUTION PROCEDURE

This work discusses on the effect of internal pressure and transverse and bending type of loading. The minimum duct thickness required to sustain the load for various ply-orientations has been obtained by using the Quadratic Failure criterion with and without buckling considerations (for the compressed side of duct).

3.1 Tsai-Wu Quadratic Failure Criterion: According to Tsai-Wu Quadratic failure criterion (7)

$$2.25[F_{xx}\sigma_x^2 + 2F_{xy}\sigma_x\sigma_y + F_{yy}\sigma_y^2 + F_{ss}\tau_{xy}^2] + 1.5[F_x\sigma_x + F_y\sigma_y] = 1$$

where,

$$F_{xx} = \frac{(1.5)^2}{XX'}; \quad F_{yy} = \frac{(1.5)^2}{YY'}; \quad F_{ss} = \frac{(1.5)^2}{S^2};$$

$$F_x = 1.5\left[\frac{1}{X} - \frac{1}{X'}\right]; \quad F_y = 1.5\left[\frac{1}{Y} - \frac{1}{Y'}\right]; \quad F^*_{xy} = \frac{F_{xy}}{\sqrt{F_{xx}F_{yy}}}$$

and $F^*_{xy} = 0.5$ based on Von Mises approach for orthotropic materials.

3.2 Buckling Failure Criterion: The criterion for failure due to buckling is described below. These relations are more conservative (8) in estimation of buckling as compared to others. If bending can be considered to be the only possible cause for deciding buckling, then the critical buckling stresses are given by equations(1).

$$M_{cr} = \pi R_0^2 h \sigma_{cr} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{cr} = \frac{Kh}{R_0} \sqrt{\frac{E_x E_y}{3(1-\nu_x \nu_y)}} \phi \quad \dots(1)$$

Where,

$$K = (1.0 - 0.901)(1 - e^{-\Psi}) \quad (\text{for axial compression})$$

$$\text{or} \quad = (1.0 - 0.731)(1 - e^{-\Psi}) \quad (\text{for bending})$$

$$\Psi = (1/16) \sqrt{\frac{R_Q}{h}}$$

$$\text{and} \quad \phi = \min. \left(\sqrt{\frac{2(1 + \sqrt{v_x v_y}) G_{xy}}{\sqrt{E_x E_y}}}, 1.0 \right)$$

4. RESULTS

The result has been presented mainly from the point of view of studying the effect of load variations on the optimum thickness of a duct subjected to complex loadings. The effects of material parameters have also been considered. The results have been given for the case when duct is subjected to a simultaneous action of internal pressure, bending moment and a shear load.

Composite ducts subjected to internal pressure experience more hoop stress as compared to the axial stress. For optimum value of the wall thickness, the best designs are those for which the fiber orientation is such that the maximum normal stresses become equal to the respective yield strengths. Figure (2) shows that this condition is satisfied for angle ply lay-up with ply-angle of about 50°. It can be seen that for fiber-orientation of about 50°, the number of plies required for fail safe design is minimum. Also with increasing pressure, the number of additional plies required is minimum in the vicinity of the same fiber-orientation and increases drastically with changing the fiber angle. Under the effect of transverse loading the wall thickness (no. of ply) is minimum (Figure 3) near the ply-angle value of about 50°.

The effect of bending moment (Figure 4) is dominant above a certain value (about 55°) of ply-angle. Below this value, bending moment effect increases less rapidly as compared to increase in load itself.

Under complex loading condition (Figures 5, 6, 7) results associated with load variation display somewhat, similar trends and may be, perhaps, obtained by superposing the effects of individual loads. Also, the minimum wall thickness is found to correspond to a fiber-angle of about 50°. It can also be seen (Figure 8) that the buckling is more dominant in a narrow range near the fiber-angle of 45°.

Figures 9 to 22 display the effect of material parameters on the optimum duct thickness with and without buckling effect. It can be inferred that the optimum ply-number for certain fixed loading condition is strongly affected by changes in the parameters α_2 and β_1 . Effect of these is also minimum for the fiber orientation of about 45°. Other α 's and β 's does have effect on optimum ply number but is insignificant when compared to those of α_2 and β_1 . It is also interesting to note that the consideration of buckling not only increases the required wall thickness (number of plies required) but also has a significant effect on the shape of the curve itself.

5. CONCLUSION

1. For the minimum weight of a duct, the fiber angle in an angle-ply lay-up should be about $40^\circ - 55^\circ$. It may also be noted that in this range, the optimum duct thickness is least affected by variations in the applied loads.
2. Among all the material parameters considered in this analysis, the duct thickness is most sensitive to parameter α_2 , the ratio of yield strength in transverse tension to the yield strength in longitudinal tension.
3. Buckling does not influence the effect of material parameters α_1 , α_3 and α_4 on the ply-orientation .
4. The study of parameters involving modulus ratios shows that β_1 , the ratio of the yield strength in longitudinal tension to the longitudinal Young's Modulus has a more significant effect on the wall thickness than the other parameters, β_2 and β_3 .

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been sponsored by Defense Advanced Projects Agency [DARPA] under contract No. MDA972-88-C-0047 for DARPA initiative in Concurrent Engineering [DICE].

7. REFERENCES

1. J. M. Whitney, On the use of shell theory for determining stresses in composite cylinders, J. of Composite Materials, vol.5, pp.340-353,(July 1971)
2. N. J. Pagano, J. C. Halpin, J. M. Whitney, Tension Buckling of Anisotropic Cylinders, J. of Composite Materials, Vol.2, pp.154,(1968)
3. R. R. Rizzo, A. A. Vicario, A Finite Element Analysis of Laminated Anisotropic Tubes Part I- A Characterization of the Off-axis Tensile Specimen, J. of Composite Materials, Vol.4, pp.360,(1970)
4. N. J. Pagano, Stress Gradients in Laminated composite cylinders, J. of Composite Materials, vol.4, pp260,(1971).
5. Robert C. Reuter Jr., Analysis of Shells under Internal Pressure, J. of Composite Materials, vol.6, pp.94-113, (Jan. 1972)
6. S. W. Tsai, Composites Design, 4th edition, Think Composites, Dayton, Ohio,1988.
7. Bhagwan D.Agrawal, J. Lawrence Broutman, Analysis and Performance of Fiber Composites, 1980, Publishers-John Wiley and Sons, New York.
8. Stephen P.Timoshenko, James M. Gere, Theory of Elastic Stability, 1961, Publishers-McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York

Figure 2: Effect of Internal Pressure Variation.

Figure 3: Effect of Transverse Load Variation.

Figure 4: Effect of Bending Load Variation.

Figure 5: Effect of Internal Pressure Variation Under Complex Loading.

Figure 6: Effect of Transverse Load Variation Under Complex Loading.

Figure 7: Effect of Bending Load Variation Under Complex Loading.

Figure 8: Effect of Buckling Under Complex Loading.

Figure 9: Effect of α_1 Variation Under Complex Loading Considering Buckling Effect.

Figure 10: Effect of α_2 Variation Under Complex Loading Considering Buckling Effect.

Figure 11: Effect of α_3 Variation Under Complex Loading Considering Buckling Effect.

Figure 12: Effect of α_4 Variation Under Complex Loading Considering Buckling Effect.

Figure 13: Effect of α_1 Variation Under Complex Loading without Buckling Effect.

Figure 14: Effect of α_2 Variation Under Complex Loading without Buckling Effect.

Figure 15: Effect of α_3 Variation Under Complex Loading without Buckling Effect.

Figure 16: Effect of α_4 Variation Under Complex Loading without Buckling Effect.

Figure 17: Effect of β_1 Variation Under Complex Loading Considering Buckling Effect.

Figure 18: Effect of β_1 Variation Under Complex Loading without Buckling Effect.

Figure 19: Effect of β_2 Variation Under Complex Loading Considering Buckling Effect.

Figure 20: Effect of β_2 Variation Under Complex Loading without Buckling Effect.

Figure 21: Effect of β_3 Variation Under Complex Loading Considering Buckling Effect.

Figure 22: Effect of β_3 Variation Under Complex Loading without Buckling Effect

